

'Simhyadi Kwath' in Management of Tamaka Shvasa – Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial

Minal Khode^{1*}, Suryaprakash Jaiswal², Jayant Gulhane³

¹Associate professor in Kayachikitsa Department of R. N. Kapoor Memorial Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital, Indore. Madhya Pradesh. Ph.D Scholar in D.M.M. Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Yavatmal.

²Professor in Kayachikitsa (DMM Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Yavatmal)

³H.O.D. and Professor in Kayachikitsa (Govt Ayurvedic College, Nagpur)

ABSTRACT

Background – In comparison to the worldwide burden of asthma, although India contributes to 13% of total asthma prevalence, it has a threefold higher DALYs, indicating a substantial gap in asthma diagnosis and treatment. **Objective:** The study design to evaluate the effect of “Simhyadi Kwath” in comparison with Tablet Doxofylline on Bronchial Asthma. **Methods-** In the open label randomized controlled clinical trial 30 patients, in trial group was treated with Simhyadi Kwath for 45 days and 30 patients in control group was managed by tablet Doxofylline for 45 days. **Assessment** was done on the basis of symptoms, severity of acute exacerbation, MRC scale and changes in Dosha. **Result-** Simhyadi Kwath is better to improve Symptoms, wheezing, MRC scale than the tablet Doxofylline by considering mean difference. Simhyadi Kwath was more significant in balancing Tridosha and changes in severity of acute exacerbation than tablet Doxofylline. **Discussion and Conclusion-** The comparative study concluded that Ayurvedic Simhyadi Kwath was more beneficial in treatment of Tamaka Shvasa with improvement in parameters without side effects.

Keywords: Bronchial Asthma, Tamaka Shvasa, Ayurvedic Treatment, Simhyadi Kwath, Tablet Doxofylline, Acute Exacerbation of Asthma, Tridosha.

INTRODUCTION

Recurrent episodes of acute Shortness of breath, typically occurring at night or in early morning hours are the cardinal manifestation of bronchial asthma. Further symptoms include cough, wheezing, feeling of tightness in the chest. ^[1] In comparison to the worldwide burden of asthma, although India contributes to 13% of total asthma prevalence, it has a threefold higher DALYs, indicating a substantial gap in asthma diagnosis and treatment.^[2]

Withdrawal Criteria - The participants were withdrawal from the trial if he / she developed any serious adverse effect or any serious condition which required ICU management Patient was refers to higher centre.

Sample Size- Control group- 30

Trial group- 30

Primary Objectives-

Evaluate the effect *Simhyadi Kwath* in management of *Tamaka Shvasa* on Symptoms, MRC Scale, *Tridosha* and severity of acute exacerbation.

Secondary Objectives-

Comparing *Simhyadi Kwath* and Tablet Doxofylline.

Study Population- 958 participants were screened to assess from which 574 had exclusion criteria, 218 had severe bronchial asthma, 38 with acute attack of exacerbation were excluded. Eligible 128 participants 90 were selected for randomization with consent for participation in study.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Randomization – Randomization done by lottery method.

Simhyadi Kwath Drugs – *Simhi [Bruhati]* (*Solanum indicum*), *Nisha [Haridra]* (*Curcuma Longa*), *Simhamukhi [Vasa]* (*Adhatoda vasica*), *Guduchi [Tinospora Cordifolia]*, *Vishva [Shunthi]* (*Zingibar officinale*), *Upakulya [pimpali]* (*Piper longum*), *Bhrunguja [Bharangi]* (*Clerodendeun serratum*), *Ghana [Nagarmotha]* (*Cyperus rotundus*) were Kwath Dravya and *Upakulya [pimpali]* (*Piper longum*), *Marich* (*Piper nigrum*) were *Prakashep* Drugs Purchased. Then first send it for standardization. After standardization, *Simhyadi Churna* was prepared by Unijules pharma, Nagpur.

Preparation of Kwath – Method of preparation of *Simhyadi Kwath* mention by the *Acharya Yogaratnakara* in *Shvasa Chikitsa*. So, the method of preparation of *Kwath* according to him with taking *Saviryataavadhi* of *Kwath* in mind, for preparation of 80 ml *Kwath*, 10 gm *Churna* was add in 160 ml water and boiled it up to 80 ml remaining in container.

Methodology - 20ml *Simhyadi Kwath* (80 ml *Kwath* divided in 4 doses) QID *Muhurmuhur* gave to 30 patients in trial group for 45 days with lukewarm water. Tablet *Doxofylline* 200 mg Bd with water was prescribed in control group of 30 patients for 45 days.

Study centre- OPD, Casualty, and camps of *Kayachikitsa* Department in Government Ayurvedic College, Nagpur after taking informed consent from the patients for clinical trial recruit in this study.

Inclusion Criteria – Patients aged between 18 to 70 years, respiratory rate was between 22 to 42 per minute, 1 to 10 years chronic patients included, went through mild to moderate exacerbation, showed positive test of reversibility by PFT, increased in FEV1 Of $\geq 12\%$ and ≥ 200 ml after of a bronchodilator, participated for 6 weeks, showed symptoms, sign and medical history of *Tamaka Shvasa*, Haemoglobin ≥ 10 gm %, ECG was normal.

Exclusion criteria- patient had severe asthma exacerbation by GINA Criteria, pregnant or lactating mother, poorly controlled Hypertension [$>160/100$ mmhg], uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus [Blood sugar fasting > 130 mg / dl and post meal 250 mg / dl], active lung disease other than Bronchial asthma, had major surgery within 2 weeks prior to screening visit and Patients with evidence of malignancy, major diseases immunosuppressant diseases like AIDS and cardio vascular diseases were excluded from this study.

Statistical Analysis - In study for data analysis paired t test and for comparison in between to drugs unpaired t test were used which is showed in the table no 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6.

Table 1: Effect of Therapy on General Symptoms Score, MRC Scale, Severity of Acute Exacerbation of 60 Patients of *Tamaka Shvasa*

S N	Symptoms	Group	Symptoms Score			% of Relief (Diff/BT)
			BT	AT	Diff	
1	<i>Shvasakastata</i>	Trial Group Control Group	85	12	73	85.88%
			89	21	68	76.40%
2	<i>Parshvashula</i>	Trial Group Control Group	58	21	37	63.79%
			62	30	32	51.61%
3	<i>Urahashula</i>	Trial Group Control Group	53	3	50	94.34%
			56	7	49	69.64%
4	<i>Kapha-shtivan</i>	Trial Group Control Group	72	15	57	79.17%
			79	39	40	50.63%
5	<i>Ghurghurak</i>	Trial Group Control Group	71	2	69	97.18%
			81	20	61	75.30%
6	<i>Aruchi</i>	Trial Group Control Group	31	10	21	67.742%
			26	23	03	11.538%
7	<i>Kasa</i>	Trial Group Control Group	65	8	57	87.69%
			65	26	39	60%

8	<i>Asino Labhate Saukhyam</i>	Trial Group Control Group	34 34	05 07	29 27	85.2% 79.41%
9	Total Score	Trial Group Control Group	469 492	76 173	393 319	83.795% 64.837%
10	Wheezing	Trial Group Control Group	71 81	2 17	69 64	97.183% 79.012%
11	MRC Scale	Trial Group Control Group	87 94	13 25	74 69	85.057% 73.404%
12	Severity of acute exacerbation	Trial Group Control Group	60 60	13 25	47 35	78.33% 58.33%

Table 2: Effect of Therapy on Symptoms, MRC Scale, Severity of Acute Exacerbation of 60 Patients of Tamaka Shvasa By Wilcoxon Singed-Rank Test

SN	SYMPTOM	GR	Mean±SD			Median		(W)	(T+)	(T-)	SD	Z	P
			BT±SD	AT±SD	MEAN DIFF.±SD	BT	AT						
1	<i>Shvasakashtata</i>	T.G	2.883 ±0.379	0.4±0.498	2.433± 0.568	3	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.7821	<0.05
		C.G	2.967±0.182	0.70±0.702	2.267±0.739	3	1	465	465	0	48.62	4.7821	<0.05
2	<i>Parshvashula</i>	T.G	1.93±0.784	0.7±0.535	1.233±0.817	2	1	325	325	0	37.17	4.372	<0.05
		C.G	2.067±0.365	1±0.454	1.06±0.449	2	1	406	406	0	43.91	4.622	<0.05
3	<i>Urahashula</i>	T.G	1.76±0.626	0.10±0.305	1.66±0.606	2	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.782	<0.05
		C.G	1.867±0.571	0.233±0.4302	1.633±0.6687	2	0	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.05
4	<i>Kaphashthivana</i>	T.G	2.4±0.674	0.5±0.508	1.9±0.7120	2.5	0.5	465	465	0	48.62	4.782	<0.05
		C.G	2.633±0.556	1.30±0.466	1.333±0.546	3	1	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.05
5	<i>Ghuraghurakam</i>	T.G	2.36±0.614	0.06±0.253	2.30±0.651	2	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.7821	<0.05
		C.G	2.7±0.535	0.666±0.546	2.033±0.808	3	1	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.05
6	<i>Aruchi</i>	T.G	1.03±0.614	0.33±0.47	0.70±0.749	1	0	153	153	0	21.12	3.6214	<0.05
		C.G	0.866±0.571	0.766±0.5613	0.1±0.3651	1	1	6	6	0	Not possible		
7	<i>Kasa</i>	T.G	2.16±0.647	0.266±0.449	1.90±0.547	2	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.7821	<0.05
		C.G	2.167±0.461	0.8667±0.4342	1.30±0.535	2	1	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.05
8	<i>Asino labhate saukhya</i>	T.G	1.13±0.34	0.166±0.37	0.96±0.41	1	0	378	378	0	41.62	4.5407	<0.05
		C.G	1.133±0.345	0.233±0.430	0.90±0.4807	1	0	325	325	0	37.17	4.3724	<0.05
10	Wheezing	T.G	2.433±0.568	0.06±0.253	2.367±0.6149	2	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.7821	<0.05
		C.G	2.70±0.535	0.566±0.504	2.133±0.7761	3	1	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.05
11	MRC Scale	T.G	2.9±0.305	0.43±0.568	2.467±0.5571	3	0	465	465	0	48.62	4.782	<0.05
		C.G	3.133±0.3457	0.833±0.6989	2.3±0.6513	3	1	465	465	0	48.62	4.782	<0.05
12	Severity of Asthma	T.G									43.91	4.622	<0.05
		C.G									32.88	4.197	<0.05

Table-3: Comparison Between Two Groups with respect to Symptoms, MRC Scale, Severity of Acute Exacerbation of Bronchial Asthma by Mann-Whitney Test

SN	Symptoms	Mean ± SD of Trial Group	Mean ± SD of Control Group	T1	T2	U'	U statistic	Z	P
1	<i>Shvasakashtata</i>	2.433±0.568	2.266±0.7397	961.5	868.5	496.5	403.5	0.68008	0.4965
2	<i>Parshvashula</i>	1.233±0.8172	1.067±0.4498	964	866	499	401	0.71704	0.47152
3	<i>Urahashula</i>	1.667±0.6065	1.633±0.6687	921	909	456	444	0.08131	0.93624
4	<i>Kapha-shtivan</i>	1.90±0.712	1.333±0.5467	1102.50	727.50	637.5	262.5	2.76469	0.00578
5	<i>Ghurghurak</i>	2.30±0.6513	2.033±0.808	993	837	528	372	1.14579	0.25014
6	<i>Aruchi</i>	0.70±0.74	0.10±0.30	1129.50	700.50	664.50	235.50	3.16387	0.0012

7	<i>Kasa</i>	1.90±0.547	1.30±0.535	1143	687	678	222	3.36346	0.00078
8	<i>Asino Labhate Saukhyam</i>	0.9667±0.4138	0.90±0.4807	943	887	478	422	0.40657	0.6818
9	Wheezing	2.30±0.6513	2.033±0.808	993	837	528	372	1.14579	0.25014
10	MRC Scale	2.467±0.5713	2.30±0.6513	973	856	508.5	391.5	0.8575	0.38978
11	Severity of acute exacerbation	1.567±0.626	0.833±0.7915	1138	692	673	227	3.28953	0.001

Table-4: Effect of Therapy on *Dosha Vriddhi Lakshan* Score of 60 Patients of *Tamaka Shvasa*

Sr. No.	<i>Dosha Lakshana</i>	Group	<i>Dosha Lakshana Score</i>			% of Relief (Diff/BT)
			BT	AT	Diff	
1	<i>Vata</i>	Trial Group	131	32	99	75.573%
		Control Group	124	75	49	39.516%
2	<i>Pitta</i>	Trial Group	69	41	28	40.58%
		Control Group	63	49	14	22.22%
3	<i>Kapha</i>	Trial Group	125	28	97	77.60%
		Control Group	112	75	37	33.036%

Table-5: Effect of Therapy on *Dosha Lakshna* of 60 Patients of *Tamaka Shvasa* By Wilcoxon Singed-Rank Test

S N	<i>Dosha Lkshana</i>	GR OUPS	Mean±SD			Median		(W)	(T+)	(T-)	SD	Z	P
			BT±SD	AT±SD	MEAN DIFF.±SD	BT	AT						
1	<i>Vata</i>	T.G	4.367 ±1.03	1.067 ±0.639	3.30 ±0.9523	4	1	465	465	0	48.62	4.78	<0.0001
		C.G	4.133 ±1.655	2.50 ±1.33	1.633 ±0.927	4	2	435	435	0	46.25	4.703	<0.0001
2	<i>Pitta</i>	T.G	2.30 ±0.7944	1.367 ±0.668	0.9333 ±0.7849	2	1	231	231	0	28.77	4.014	<0.0001
		C.G	2.10 ±1.322	1.633 ±1.098	0.466 ±0.7303	2	1	66	66	0	11.25	2.934	<0.0001
3	<i>Kapha</i>	T.G	4.167 ±1.053	0.9333 ±0.7397	3.233 ±0.9353	4	1	465	465	0	48.62	4.782	<0.0001
		C.G	3.733 ±0.944	2.50 ±0.861	1.233 ±0.7739	4	2	351	351	0	39.32	4.45	<0.0001

Table-6: Comparison Between Two Groups with respect to *Dosha* by Mann-Whitney Test

S N	<i>Dosha</i>	Mean±SD of T.G.	Mean ± SD of C.G	T1	T2	U'	U stat	Z	P
1	<i>Vata</i>	3.30 ±0.9523	1.633 ±0.9279	1268	562	803	97	5.21151	<0.0001
2	<i>Pitta</i>	0.9333 ±0.7849	0.4667 ±0.7303	1075	755	610	290	2.35812	0.0170
3	<i>Kapha</i>	3.233 ±0.9353	1.233 ±0.7739	1304	526	839	61	5.74375	<0.0001

Graphical Presentation-

Figure-1: Effect of Therapy on General Symptoms Score of 60 Patients of Tamaka Shvasa

Figure -2: Effect of Therapy On Dosha Lakshna of 60 Patients of Tamaka Shvasa By Wilcoxon-Ranked Singed Test

RESULT

Simhydi Kwath was Valuable drug of choice in improvement of all *Tamaka Shvasa* symptoms. *Simhyadi Kwath* was responsible to change *Shvasakashtata* from 2.833±0.379 to 0.4±0.498, *Parshvashula* from 1.93±0.784 to 0.7±0.535, *Urahashula* from 1.76±0.626 to 0.10±0.305, *Kapha-Shtivana* from 2.4±0.674 to 0.5±0.508, *Ghurghurakama* from 2.36±0.614 to 0.06±0.253, *Aruchi* from 1.03±0.614 to 0.33±0.47, *Kasa* from 2.16±0.647 to 0.266±0.449, *Asino Labhate Soukhyam* from 1.13±0.34 to 0.166±0.37, wheezing from

2.433±0.568 to 0.06±0.253, MRC Scale from 2.9±0.305 to 0.43±0.568 than tablet Doxofylline by considering mean difference. Tablet Doxofylline was use to change *Shvasakashtata* from 2.967±0.182 to 0.70±0.702, *Parshvashula* from 2.067±0.365 to 1±0.454, *Urahashula* from 1.867±0.571 to 0.233±0.4302, *Kapha-Shtivana* from 2.633±0.556 to 1.30±0.466, *Ghurghurakama* from 2.7±0.535 to 0.666±0.546, *Aruchi* from 0.866±0.571 to 0.766±0.5613, *Kasa* from 2.167±0.461 to 0.8667±0.4342, *Asino Labhate Soukhyam* from 1.133±0.345 to 0.233±0.430, wheezing from 2.70±0.535 to 0.566±0.504, MRC Scale from

3.133±0.3457 to 0.833±0.6989. It was observed that *Simhyadi Kwath* is more effective to treat the not only symptoms of *Tamaka Shvasa* but also reduce MRC Scale than tablet Doxofylline as considering the mean difference of both drugs. *Simhyadi Kwath* balances vitiated *Vata* by changing from 4.367±1.03 to 1.067±0.639 with vitiated *Kapha* by changing from 4.167±1.053 to 0.9333±0.7397 with vitiated *Pitta* by changing from 2.30±0.7944 to 1.367±0.668. Tablet Doxofylline is not more helpful to balance the vitiated *Dosha* as considering the mean difference than *Simhyadi Kwath*.

Simhyadi Kwath is advantageous for decreasing severity of asthma by 78.33% than tablet Doxofylline to reduce severity of asthma by 58.33%. *Simhyadi Kwath* is more profitable in improving total score by 83.795% than tablet Doxofylline which improve it by 64.837%.

DISCUSSION

Breathlessness is cause due to narrowed airway in lungs because of inflammation, bronchoconstriction and excess mucus formation in bronchial asthma. In *Simhyadi Kwath* contains *Haridra*, *Guduchi*, *Maricha*, *Pippali*, *Shunthi* has anti-inflammatory property, with *Vasa*, *Pimpali* work as a bronchodilator and *Shunthi*, *Maricha* plays role for Anti-catarrhal agents. Sputum expectoration cause by chronic inflammation in the airways leading to mucus hypersecretions and increased mucus production in response to triggers like allergens, pollutants and viral infection mainly seen in bronchial asthma. *Haridra*, *Guduchi*, *Maricha*, *Pippali*, *Shunthi* work as an anti-inflammatory with *Haridra*, *Bharangi*, *Guduchi* work as an anti-allergy with *Shunthi*, *Maricha* work as an anti-catarrhal, and *Vasa* work as an Expectorant. Wheezing caused by inflammation and excess mucus secretions leading to narrowing of airway and reduce airflow creating a high-pitched whistling sound as the air is force to the constricted passage which is a cardinal sign in bronchial asthma. For normal airflow in respiratory organs *Simhyadi Kwath* gets tremendous results due to anti-inflammatory action of *Haridra*, *Guduchi*, *Maricha*, *Pippali*, *Shunthi* with anti-allergy action of *Haridra*, *Bharangi*, *Guduchi* with anti-tissue action of *Vasa*, *Shunthi* with Bronchodilator action of *Vasa*, *Pimpali* with Anti-

catarrhal action of *Shunthi*, *Maricha* with anti-spasmodic action of *Vasa* with Expectorant action of *Vasa*. Recurrent cough and cold with breathlessness are treated by *Simhyadi Kwath* due to immunomodulator action of *Guduchi* and *Pippali*. *Simhyadi Kwath* balancing *Tridosha* by *Kaphaghna* 40%, *Pittaghna* 25%, *Vataghna* 35%, *Vata-kaphaghna* 50%, *Pitta-Kaphaghna* 30%, *Tridoshgghna* 20% property by considering *Rasa*, *Virya* and *Vipaka* of *Simhyadi Kwath* and its *Prakashhepa Dravya*.

CONCLUSION

Simhyadi Kwath is beneficial in *Tamaka Shvasa* (Bronchial Asthama) to reduce symptoms and severity of asthma by *Sampraptibhanga*, improve MRC scale along with Balancing *Tridosha*.

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HOW TO CITE: Sneha Minal Khode*, Suryaprakash Jaiswal, Jayant Gulhane, 'Simhyadi Kwath' in Management of Tamaka Shvasa – Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (10), 206-212. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17313168>

